

EFFECT OF THERMAL CYCLING ON THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF CFRP FOR PRECISE SPACE STRUCTURE

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ABSTRACT

Thermal cycle tests were conducted on carbon fiber reinforced poly-cyanate ester and epoxy resin which were candidate materials for precise space structure. From surface observation, transverse cracks in 90° layers and delamination were confirmed to occur. Bending modulus, however did not decrease. This fact suggest that the damages were superficial phenomena.

1 INTRODUCTION

A large antenna on orbit is useful equipment for the field of radio astronomy and communication technologies. As a higher accuracy antenna reflector, a deployable reflector composed by tensioned radial ribs and circumferential cable structure build on a truss structure were proposed. Under space environment, variations in temperature, for example, in and out of the Earth's shadow, cause cyclic thermal deformation of the structure, which reduces accuracy of the geometry and resultant resolution of the antenna. In order to overcome this situation, Carbon-fiber-reinforced plastics (CFRP) are expected as a candidate material. Coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) of carbon fiber is less than 0. Thus zero CTE of CFRP laminate might be attained if an appropriate laminate configuration is designed. On the other hand, in the laminate, mismatch of the thermal expansion coefficients between plies of different orientations causes thermal residual stress which becomes the main reason for matrix cracking. Moreover, cyclic temperature variations cause cyclic thermal stress condition. It is very important to clarify the microscopic damage development in CFRP laminates under thermal cycling in the view of the practical use because such damages affect mechanical properties of CFRP, such as elastic modulus. Previously, microscopic damage behavior in CFRP laminates under cyclic thermal loading has been investigated by many researchers [1-4]. However, little study about variation in mechanical properties under cyclic thermal loading [5]. In the present study, we selected PAN -based high modulus carbon fiber as reinforcements and Epoxy and polycyanate as matrices, designed and fabricate CFRP laminates which has nearly zero CTE. Cyclic thermal impact tests were conducted on both types of specimens to clarify the microscopic damage behavior. Bending tests were also conducted to discuss effect of microscopic damage on mechanical properties.

2 EXPERIMENTS

Material systems used, laminate configurations and geometries were shown in Table 1. M46J is PAN based high modulus carbon fiber. Poly-cyanate ester resin has much lower hygroscopic absorption properties. In the remaining part, we referred the type of specimen as the symbol defined in table 1. Laminates were stacked in width direction as shown in Fig. 1, which are different from general composites. Laminate configurations were designed as 0 thermal expansion coefficient. Specimen

surfaces were polished and finished using 0.03 μ m alumina suspension. Before testing, specimens were dried in a vacuum desiccator to avoid moisture effect.

In order to simulate thermal loading under space environment (-170°C~120°C), we used an electric furnace (120°C, DK-240S, Yamato) and liquid nitrogen (LN2, -197°C). At first specimens were put in an electric furnace with temperature 120°C for 10 min., then they were put in a foam carton filled with LN2 for 5 min. This cycle was repeated up to 600 cycles. Surface observations and initial elastic modulus measurement were conducted periodically.

Surface observation was conducted using a video microscope system (VW-5000, Keyence). Observation area is 25 mm at the center of the specimen. We defined transverse crack density as the number of cracks per unit observation length. Outermost 90° layer was termed as 1st90° layer. Similarly, 2nd90°, 3rd90° and 4th90° were also defined.

Elastic modulus variation was measured by three-point bending testing using universal testing machine (AG-1000A, Shimadzu). Span length was 140 mm. During tests, specimen deflection and load were measured with a dial gauge (DT-10D, Kyowa) and a load cell (LUR-A50NSAI, Kyowa), respectively. Only a tiny deflection, which gives 0.2% strain, was loaded.

Table 1 Specimens configurations and geometries.

Symbol	Matrix	Fiber	Stacking Sequence	(width[mm])x(thickness[mm])
CM	Polycyanate	M46J	[0/30/90/-30/0] _{4S}	(4.32±0.01)x(1.48±0.03)
EM	Epoxy	M46J	[0/30/90/-30/0] _{4S}	(3.66±0.02)x(1.55±0.01)

Fig. 1 Geometry of specimen.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Microscopic damages observed during thermal cycles were transverse cracks in 90° layers and delamination. Figure 1 shows transverse crack density as a function of number of cycles. Transverse crack density was larger in 1st90° layer of each specimen at the early stage of cycles. Crack accumulation in 2nd90°, 3rd90° and 4th90° layers is faster in CM specimen than in EM. This is due to lower matrix toughness of poly-cyanate ester. In EM specimen, transverse crack density in 2nd90°, 3rd90° and 4th90° layers increased linearly with number of cycles. In CM specimen transverse crack density in 2nd90°, 3rd90° and 4th90° layers became larger than in 1st90° layer. This is due to the lower stress recovery between cracks in 1st90° layer. Delamination occurred at the tip of cracks and grew in length as shown in Fig. 2, which damage inhibited stress recovery caused by shear stress at the interface.

Figures 2 and 3 shows damage progress in CM and EM specimens, respectively. As mentioned above delamination occurred at the tip of cracks. Crack opening displacement became larger with cycles.

Figure 4 shows bending modulus as a function of number of cycles. Moduli of both CM and EM specimen remain constant up to 600 cycles. Based on the classical lamination theory, the 90° layers carry about 4% of the whole loading. This fact is coincident with the observation results of no damages in 0° layers. Furthermore, no reduction in moduli indicated the damages, such as transverse cracks in 90° layers and delamination were surface superficial phenomena. That is, the damages did not grow in width direction of the specimen.

(a) CM

(b) EM

Figure 1 Transverse crack density as a function of number of thermal cycles.

(a) Crack growth of 1st90° of specimen CM at 1cycle.

10 μ m

(b) Crack growth of 1st90° of specimen CM at 600cycles.

10 μ m

Figure 2 Crack growth in 1st 90° ply of CM.

(a) Crack growth of 1st90° of specimen EM at 1cycle.

10 μ m

(b) Crack growth of 1st90° of specimen EM at 600cycles.

10 μ m

Figure 3 Crack progress in Specimen EM.

(a) CM

(b) EM

Figure 4 Elastic modulus as a function of number of cycles.

4 CONCLUSION

In the present study, two types of CFRP laminate, such as PAN-based high modulus carbon fiber/polycyanate ester resin (CM) and epoxy resin (EM), with near 0 thermal expansion coefficient were prepared as candidate materials for a large precise space structure. Thermal cycle tests were conducted on the specimens to simulate space environment. For CM, transverse cracks occurred at the initial stage of the tests. Delamination also occurs from the tip of transverse cracks with increasing thermal

cycles. Modulus did not change up to 600 thermal cycles. This results indicated the damages were only occurred on the surface of the specimen and did not grow in the width direction.

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